

A STUDY OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL FEMALE TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR MARITAL STATUS, EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION AND CASTE CATEGORY

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence is one of the vital characteristics of personality and it is the key to gain success in one's life . It contains the competency of managing and observing self and others. It is a combination of interpersonal and intrapersonal skills for understanding life's aims. A teacher is the foundation of the society .Teachers perform a central role in preparing students to develop knowledge, sympathetic, and responsible contributor of society . The present work aim to synthesize the available data by both quantitative and quantitative analysis .The mean objective was to study the emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding marital status, educational qualification and caste category. The present research was conducted on 100 female teachers Dr Shubhara Mangal Emotional intelligence inventory used to measure emotional intelligence. Finding of the study shows that there is no significant difference between married and unmarried female teachers, undergraduate and postgraduate female teacher and reserved and unreserved female teacher.

Key Point Emotional intelligence, secondary school female teacher.

Introduction

Education is the procedure of promoting learning, gaining of skills, moral beliefs, knowledge and habits. Informal manner of education seen in the way of self-directed learning, life experience and transmission of culture from generation to generation. In formal education we need a teacher and school for proper learning. A teacher is a main pillar of formal education

that opens the door of knowledge for the student. Teacher is essential for the proper growth and progress of the student. Each student is different from others and needs special care. Teachers also provide a special care to every student to promote the special ability and success in life depending upon how a person faces fluctuation in life. Emotional intelligence is one of the important factors for a teacher to relay their teaching ability in adjectable manners.

According to Elias: "Emotional competency is the ability to understand, manage and Express the emotional aspect of one's life in ways that enable the successful management of tasks such as learning, forming relationships, solving everyday problems, and adapting to the complex demands of growth and development. Emotional intelligence helps a teacher increase their productivity in school and career also. Emotionally intelligent teachers make notable self decisions, utilising their emotions as a medium of energy and Direction. They live with integrity and effectively solve their problems. Emotionally intelligent teacher protectively coordinate with student and other person and effectively guide the student ."It performs a crucial act in the development of the personal and social area of a human. In today's time teaching work is full of difficulties. It is difficult for a teacher to control their emotions in the classroom. They couldn't handle their irritating behaviour during lecture time. The major factor behind this behaviour is workload and when we talk about female teachers, she has double workload; household work and professional work .A teacher not only have lecture work but have different academic work like prepare question paper, maintain records, prepare report card and other curriculum activities. Emotional intelligence is an important component that helps the teacher to balance the behaviour in the classroom.

The aim of the research is to study the emotional intelligence of the female teacher with respect to marital status, Educational qualification, locality and category.

Review of the Literature

Kritika and Rukari Santosh (2023) The topic of the study was Impact of emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers on teaching styles. The Objective of the study was to define the concept of emotional intelligence and impact of emotional intelligence of teachers on using of teaching style they use Dr. S.K. Mangal and Dr. Subrah Mangal standardised emotional inventory for data collection. The total number of the sample is 140 teachers from Mandsaur district and 70 from Neemuch district, out of 70 teachers there were 35 government school teachers and 35 private school teachers of the secondary school. The first hypothesis was the study teaching style of the secondary school teacher are independent from the

emotional intelligence of the teacher. the second hypothesis of the study was the teaching style of the secondary school teachers dependent on the emotions of the secondary school teachers. After analysis the result shows that there is a positive correlation between the emotional intelligence of the teacher and the teaching style used by the secondary school teacher.

Bhuriyaan Neha (2021) The topic of the study A study of emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender. The main objective of the study is to find out the emotional intelligence level of teachers with respect to their gender. The sample of the study was 100 secondary teachers. Results shows that there is a significant difference in emotional intelligence of private Secondary School teachers with respect to gender.

Bhuvneshwari G.and Baskaran.D. (2020) investigator investigated the topic A study of emotional intelligence of Higher Secondary School teachers in Chengalpatha district. This was a survey method study. The researcher includes 350 secondary school teachers in the research they used Alexander emotional in inventory for collecting data. the study shows a significant difference between the level of emotional intelligence of Higher Secondary School teachers. There is a significant difference between the emotional intelligence of urban secondary school teachers and rural Secondary School teachers.

Mehta Sandhya 2015 studied the topic The study personality and emotional intelligence of teachers.The total sample of the study was 300 they were 26% male and 74% were female. further 82% married and 18% unmarried. the result of the study includes that there is a significant difference between Government and private school teachers. Government teachers are higher than private teachers.

Chandra, Akhilesh (2012) He investigated the topic A study of teacher effectiveness in relation to emotional intelligence, mental health, job satisfaction and personality of secondary school teachers. The research has been conducted on the secondary school teachers of Budaun district . The sample includes 250 male and 250 female teachers. The result of the study is that high and low effective teachers differ significantly in relation to emotional intelligence.

Kant, Ravi & Lanka Kumar Samir (2012) researcher investigated the topic, Emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers in relation to their professional development. This was a survey study in the Rampur district of Uttar Pradesh with a sample of 120 secondary teachers. the used Amurkoo Hyde emotional intelligence scale for collecting data. The result of the study found that there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and professional development of secondary school teachers. They concluded that different

dimensions of emotional intelligence such as self awareness, empathy, stability, managing, integrity, self development, value orientation, altruistic behaviour have no significant difference with professional development but have a significant difference between male and female emotional intelligence.

D.Ponmozhi & T.Ezhibharathy (2012) this study was conducted in the district of Cuddalore district Tamilnadu. This was a normative survey. The sample of the study was 150 teachers. Finding the study present, most of the teachers have high emotional intelligence. There was a significant difference in emotional intelligence on the basis of age group and locality but the difference of the emotional intelligence of Government and private teachers was not significant.

Significance of the study:-

Emotional intelligency of the female teacher help to manage their emotion effectively. Teachers with high emotional intelligence can adopted to emotion needs of their students and enhance the supportive learning. it can help to improved students and teacher relationships and lead to better connection and trust with them. it also help to a female teachers to manage professional and household demands and work to cope with stress, avoid Burnout and solve conflicts. emotional intelligence of a teacher contribute to a collaborative and harmonious school culture by managing interpersonal relations effectively and help to better outcome of students.

Objectives of the research:-

- 1.To study the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers with respect to marital status.
- 2.To study the emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding educational qualification.
3. To study the emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding categories.
- 4.To study the emotional Intelligence of secondary School female teacher regarding Marital status educational qualification and cast category

Hypothesis:-

H01. There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of married and unmarried Secondary School female teachers .

H02. There is no significance between the emotional intelligence of undergraduate and higher educated secondary school female teachers

H03. There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of reserved and unreserved secondary school female teachers

H04. There is no significant difference among the emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding marital status ,educational qualification and caste category.

Delimitations of the study:-

1. The sample has been committed to 100 secondary school teachers only.
2. The study was restricted to Secondary School female teachers only.
3. The study was restricted to the government and aided government school .
4. The Study was restricted to the Meerut District of Uttar Pradesh .
5. Only survey method is used to collect the data.

Methodology of the research

Methodology is the essential part of the research. It refers to the systematic theoretical analysis of the methods that are applied in the field of the study. It comprises the principle theories and approaches that research pursues together to analyse and interpret data .It also clarifies the rationale behind choosing those techniques. It provide a Framework for understanding how research is executed.

Population:-In this study include all government and aided government Secondary School teacher from Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh

Sample:- The total sample of the study is 100 female teachers from the Govt. /Aided government secondary school of Meerut district .

Variable:-

independent variables :-Marital status, Educational qualification, locality, caste category

Dependent Variable :-Emotional intelligence

Operational Definition :-

Emotional intelligence (EI):-Emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to understand, manage, perceive, handle and use the emotion of itself and another person.

Secondary School:- Teachers who teach and instruct students from class 6-12 Govt. and aided government schools. The secondary school teachers have the mastery in subjects such as English, Hindi, Science Social, science ,Maths, Art or any other subjects.

Tool used

Emotional intelligence scale developed by Dr(mrs) Shubhra Mangal. This tool constructed for secondary and senior secondary school teachers. This scale includes 200 items which consists 106 positive and 94 negative items. Test-retest Reliability coefficient of scale 0.96 and split half Reliability is 0.95. The validity of the scale has 0.55.

Statistical Analysis:-

H01. There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of married and unmarried Secondary School female teachers.

Table 1. difference between the emotional intelligence of married and unmarried Secondary School female teachers

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
	EI MARRIED	EI UN MARRIED
Mean	754.05	749.025
Variance	6859.302542	3635.717308
Observations	60	40
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	97	
t Stat	0.350777634	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.363257922	
t Critical one-tail	1.66071461	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.726515845	
t Critical two-tail	1.984723186	

The above table 1.0 it inferred that the mean score value of married teacher is 754.05 and the mean score value of unmarried female teacher is 749.025. The calculated 't' value is 0.35 077 and the critical value 1.984. Critical value is greater than the calculated t value. Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between married and unmarried female secondary school teachers is accepted. which show that there is no difference between emotional intelligence of married and unmarried teachers.

H02. There is no significance between the emotional intelligence of undergraduate and higher educated (postgraduate)secondary school female teachers.

Table1. Difference between emotional intelligence of married and unmarried female secondary school teachers

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
	EI UG	EI PG
Mean	769.3823529	757.0757576
Variance	10712.00089	6633.148019
Observations	34	66
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	55	
t Stat	0.603699035	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.274262833	
t Critical one-tail	1.673033965	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.548525667	
t Critical two-tail	2.004044783	

The above table 2.0. It inferred that the mean score value of undergraduate teachers is 769.38 and the mean score value of postgraduate female teacher is 757.075. The calculated ‘t’ value is 0.60369 and the critical value is 2.00. Critical value is greater than the calculated t value .Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between undergraduate female teachers and postgraduate female secondary school teachers is accepted. which shows that there is no difference between the emotional intelligence of undergraduates and postgraduate teachers.

H03. There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of reserved and unreserved secondary school female teachers .

Table 3. Difference between emotional intelligence of reserved and unreserved female secondary school teachers

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
	reserved	unreserved
Mean	765.3928571	756.3333333
Variance	5234.617725	7138.084507
Observations	28	72
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	57	
t Stat	0.535615953	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.297153923	
t Critical one-tail	1.672028888	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.594307846	
t Critical two-tail	2.002465459	

The above table 3.0. It inferred that the mean score value of reserved teachers is 765.39 and the mean score value of unreserved female teacher is 756.33. The calculated 't' value is 0.5356 and the critical value is 2.00. Critical value is greater than the calculated t value. Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between reserved female teachers and unreserved female secondary school teachers is accepted. which shows that there is no difference between the emotional intelligence of reserved and unreserved teachers.

H04. There is no significant difference among the emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding marital status, educational qualification and caste category.

Table 4 different among emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding marital status educational qualification and caste category

Anova: Single Factor							
SUMMARY							
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance			
marital status	100	75204	752.04	5526.240808			
educational qualification	100	76126	761.26	7960.093333			
Caste category	100	75887	758.87	6563.568788			
ANOVA							
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	
Between Groups	4578.98	2	2289.49	0.342568741	0.71022446	3.026153369	
Within Groups	1984940.39	297	6683.300976				
Total	1989519.37						

The calculated 'f' value is 0.3426 and the critical value is 3.026. Critical value is greater than the calculated f value .Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant difference among the emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding marital status ,educational qualification and caste are accepted. which shows that there is no difference among the emotional intelligence of secondary school female teachers regarding marital status, educational qualification and caste category.

Conclusion :- The findings of the hypothesis shows that there was no difference between married and unmarried secondary school female teachers. No difference was found between the emotional intelligence of undergraduate and postgraduate Secondary School female teachers.and there was not a difference between emotional intelligence of reserved and unreserved secondary school female teachers. Finding also explained that there was not a difference among emotional intelligence on the bases of marital status , educational qualification and caste category .

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